

Strengthening Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) in the Institutes of the Leibniz Association, Phase 2: Towards Open Research Information

Matthias Goeritz ^{1,2}, Philipp Steglich ¹

¹ IT, Leibniz Association (Headquarters), Berlin, Germany

² Leibniz Competition, Leibniz Association (Headquarters), Berlin, Germany

Significance of CRIS and research information management

Systematic, well-founded, and sustainable research information management based on established standards has become indispensable for leading scientific organizations. The Leibniz Association, as an excellent, decentralized science organization comprising 96 independent research institutes and museums throughout Germany, launched its initiative “Strengthening Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) in the Institutes of the Leibniz Association” in November 2022.

CRIS systems are sophisticated databases or information systems meticulously designed to store, manage, and exchange contextual metadata for research activities and integrate and link various elements of the complex research ecosystem. CRIS systems are essential catalysts for enhancing visibility, supporting informed decision-making processes, and enabling data-driven strategic development.

The “Strengthening CRIS” initiative aims to promote CRIS adoption and implement open research information principles across the Leibniz Association, in line with the Barcelona Declaration.

Strategic objectives of the Strengthening CRIS initiative

Interoperability, openness, and community building are cornerstones of an effective CRIS strategy. Consequently, the initiative serves multiple strategic purposes:

1. Advancing research information management: Improvements in research information management foster scientific collaboration and the visibility of research work and findings and their (societal) impact. They also support and optimize the institute’s decision-making, strategic planning and reporting obligations.
2. Ensuring interoperability, standardization, and openness: The initiative strongly promotes the adoption of national and international standards like the Kerndatensatz Forschung standard in Germany (KDSF) or the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF). Standardization also includes the desirable widespread use of persistent identifiers (PIDs). This focus on standardization ensures

interoperability, which is crucial for facilitating data exchange, enabling cross-institutional collaboration, and participating in larger research networks and infrastructures. It is necessary for the open sharing of research information, as well as for integrating research information from external sources.

3. Building a community for research information and CRIS within the Leibniz Association: Those interested in CRIS often have an interface function in their institutions and may have very different professional backgrounds. Our regular surveys show that they usually come from reporting, research administration, IT, and libraries, but other areas are also represented. The diversity of individual professional backgrounds, experiences, and knowledge is a great asset, but it also requires ongoing discussion to develop a common perspective on the challenges and possible solutions. Such a community is essential for the exchange of experiences, mutual support, and the comprehensive implementation of standards and best practice. It provides an important basis for the continuous development of research information management in the Leibniz Association and for the open provision of research information from the Leibniz Association and its institutes.

In January 2023, only 23 of the 96 Leibniz institutes were using a CRIS system. Since the launch of the initiative, 17 additional Leibniz institutes have joined, either having already introduced a system, or being in the process of implementing one, or planning to do so. This demonstrates the initiative's effectiveness in driving CRIS adoption across the Leibniz Association and highlights the growing recognition of CRIS's importance among member institutes. An important milestone was the signing of the Barcelona Declaration by the Leibniz Association in June 2024. Commitment to the goals defined in the declaration forms the basis for disseminating the principle of open research information in the Leibniz institutes.

Approach and key activities

A multi-pronged approach is necessary to ensure success with CRIS. To achieve its ambitious goals, the initiative combines direct support, knowledge-sharing, community-building, and strategic planning:

1. Direct support and advice: The initiative offers tailored support to Leibniz institutes on open research information and CRIS, including consulting services, implementation assistance, and expertise building. It also provides financial support for external consultancy services through a framework agreement.
2. Focus on openness: The initiative is placing increased emphasis on the principle of open research information, in accordance with the Barcelona Declaration, as well as open-source CRIS systems. Three self-developed or co-developed open-source CRIS systems (GRIS, OSIRIS, and VIVO) are already being used successfully within the Leibniz Association. The initiative supports the further development and adoption of these systems. Many Leibniz institutes have expressed great interest in these open-source CRIS systems and more than ten are currently planning an implementation.
3. National and international networking: The initiative fosters collaboration with other German non-university research organizations, the DINI Working Group on Research Information and its Systems (DINI AG FIS), the PID Network Germany, and the Commission for Research Information in Germany (KFiD). Internationally, it cooperates with euroCRIS and the CRISCROS working group. At the euroCRIS conference in May 2024, the initiative presented its work in a poster session. The

poster is available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10961102>
An updated version of this poster with a stronger focus on the specific activities of the initiative's second funding phase ("Towards Open Research Information") was shown at the Bologna Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata (WOOC2025). This poster is also available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15487914>

4. Knowledge-sharing and community-building: A cornerstone of the initiative is the organization of regular online workshops covering both overarching CRIS topics and specific CRIS products. These workshops have become vital platforms for knowledge exchange and community-building within the Leibniz Association, enabling Leibniz institutes to learn from each other's experiences and discuss common challenges.
5. Annual CRIS Days: The initiative organizes annual two-day in-person workshops known as "CRIS Days". These events provide an excellent opportunity for in-depth experience exchange, networking, and collaborative problem-solving. They also feature live demonstrations of various CRIS systems used within the Leibniz Association, allowing participants to gain hands-on insights. Nearly all 96 Leibniz institutes participate in these networking opportunities in person or online, derive benefits from them, and are involved in the Leibniz CRIS community.
6. Online resources: A comprehensive, publicly available Wiki (<https://www.leibniz.wiki/cris>) has been created to document activities and workshops, and provide up-to-date information on CRIS topics. This regularly updated Wiki is a valuable knowledge resource for all Leibniz institutes.
7. CRIS profiles: The initiative has created detailed CRIS profiles, where experts from within the Leibniz Association record and update information on the CRIS systems used in their institutes. These profiles include information on many relevant aspects, are invaluable in helping institutions make informed decisions about specific CRIS systems, and provide inspiration for potential further developments.
8. Updating the IDA data model: The data model of the "Information system for data collection and analysis" (IDA) at Leibniz Headquarters was updated to improve the prerequisites for using the IDA API, to facilitate better data integration and reporting capabilities across the Leibniz Association. It is an important basis for the possible future open dissemination of Leibniz research information.

Challenges and lessons learned

Promoting the use of CRIS and the open availability of research information across 96 Leibniz institutes – taking into account Germany's federal structure – presents a series of challenges, from which the following principles can be derived:

The cross-institutional development of CRIS requires a strong community. In a well-functioning community, institutes with more experience can support those with less, exchange knowledge about standards and best practices, and collaborate at all levels. This advances the efforts of all institutes and the association as a whole.

Ongoing and repeated communication with all stakeholders is essential. The Leibniz Association does not have a top-down structure. Therefore, it is all the more important to communicate with all stakeholders, to remind them frequently of CRIS and research information topics, and to ensure that all parties are working towards a common goal.

Research information management must extend beyond one's own institute. In the past, research information management in the Leibniz Association often focused on specific reporting obligations. However, to be visible on a national and international level, institutes and organizations must ensure that they disseminate information about their research more widely and make it accessible to all interested parties.

Open science principles must also be applied to research information and CRIS. Research information must be visible and available; otherwise, the research itself is not visible. This can only be ensured by adhering to the principle of openness. The use of open-source CRIS systems is particularly helpful in this regard, as they do not carry the risk of vendor lock-in and do not confine research information within a profit-maximizing proprietary ecosystem.

Sustainable structures and standards are needed for open access to research information. To provide, verify, and retrieve research information openly, various software systems must communicate with each other. This is only possible through the establishment of and adherence to international standards. Moreover, research information can only be made openly available if overarching structures exist and are supported by the community.

Future focus

The Strengthening CRIS initiative has been very well received by Leibniz institutes and is constantly being developed further, based on the latest advances in the CRIS field. A large and vibrant professional community of CRIS experts and individuals interested in using CRIS has formed across all 96 Leibniz institutes.

Open-source CRIS and open research information enhance scientific sovereignty and visibility. Consequently, the initiative plans to focus on several key areas:

1. Further distribution and use of open-source CRIS
2. Promotion of open research information, and support for and use of open data sources such as OpenAIRE and OpenAlex
3. Development of interfaces between systems (APIs)
4. Dissemination of standards and persistent identifiers (PIDs) in the Leibniz Association

In conclusion, the Strengthening CRIS initiative plays a crucial role in advancing the digital capabilities of the Leibniz Association. By promoting the adoption and effective use of CRIS, it contributes to enhancing the visibility, efficiency, and strategic development of the Leibniz Association and its member institutes as well as the open sharing of research information. The initiative's focus on the principles of openness aligns with broader trends in the scientific community, moving the Leibniz Association ahead in the area of open research information management, all through the implementation and ongoing development of CRIS.

References

Goeritz, Matthias, Prinzensing, Gregor & Steglich, Philipp. (2024). Strengthening Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) in the Institutes of the Leibniz Association. 16th International Conference on Current Research Information Systems: Emerging trends for international collaboration in the CRIS domain (CRIS2024), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10961102>

Goeritz, Matthias, Prinzensing, Gregor & Steglich, Philipp. (2025). Strengthening Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) in the Institutes of the Leibniz Association, Phase 2: Towards Open Research Information. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15487914>